

Comparisons of total power loss measurements performed by Epstein frame using revised procedures at room temperature

Final report

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1 Introduction

Two experimental setups are currently used for the measurement of power losses in magnetic steels – the Epstein frame and the Single Sheet Tester (SST). To date, a number of intercomparisons, promoted by EURAMET and the IEC TC 68 have confirmed good reproducibility for both the Epstein and SST methods, with an uncertainty around 1 % for the power loss measurement. These comparisons, however, were only focused on measurements at 50 Hz and room temperature [1].

Within the HEFMAG project a new reference round robin comparison was performed between Epstein frames and SST at 50 Hz and 100 Hz using non-oriented and grain-oriented samples. In addition, a new Epstein round robin comparison up to higher frequencies of 10 kHz using non-oriented and Fe₅₀Co₅₀ sheets was performed.

As an output of the round robin test a number of documents will be drafted in parallel to the conductance of the measurements. At all stages of the round robin test these documents shall reflect the current state of knowledge:

1. Report of measurement results: This document contains the results of measurements and their accuracy for each method and each laboratory and a discussion of the findings during the round robin comparison. This report will be shared through a report to IEC TC 68 and made available to the stakeholders.
2. A Good practice guide on the measurement of power losses in non-oriented steels and grain-oriented materials using standard measurement setups at room temperature will be developed for end users This document will provide the basis for discussions on CMC revisions and updates of some of the IEC 60404 standards within the IEC TC 68.

2 Reference samples

The aim of this task is to evaluate and reduce the uncertainty of Epstein frame power loss measurements for low and high frequencies from 50 Hz to 10 kHz at room temperature according to IEC 60404-2 (or if necessary IEC 60404-10).

Six Epstein samples were prepared for the comparison. The transfer standards are samples of grain-oriented (GO) and non-oriented (NO) electrical steel:

- two samples of NO steel in the form of strips for Epstein frame measurements with a weight of at least 240 g for the 700 turns Epstein (according to IEC 60404-2) and no less than 12 strips for the 100 turns or 200 turns Epstein (according to IEC 60404-10). The quantity of the strips in the sample must be a multiple of 4 and rolling direction must be considered. Thickness will be approximately 0.2 mm (NO 0.2) and 0.3 mm (NO 0.3).
- three samples of GO steel in the form of strips for Epstein frame measurements with a weight of at least 240 g for the 700 turns Epstein (according to IEC 60404-2) and no less than 12 strips for the 100 turns or 200 turns Epstein (according to IEC 60404-10). The quantity of the strips in the sample must be a multiple of 4 and rolling direction must be considered. Thickness will be approximately 0.18 mm (GO 0.18), 0.2 mm (Laser scribed 0.2) and 0.3 mm (GO 0.3).
- sample of Fe₅₀Co₅₀ steel sheets in the form of Epstein strips (minimum 12) and thickness of approximately 0.2 mm (FeCo 0.2). The quantity of the strips in the sample must be a multiple of 4. The sample will be used for measurement at frequencies up to 10 kHz.

All samples were demagnetized prior to measurement.

3 Measurements to be made

3.1 *Quantity to be measured*

Measurements of specific total power loss P_s (W/kg) of the Epstein samples were performed according to the standard IEC 60404-2 (up to 400 Hz) and IEC 60404-10 (above 400 Hz) using optimized experimental Epstein setups for power loss measurements under standard conditions.

The magnetic polarization J_m was measured at $H_m = 800$ A/m in the GO strips and at $H_m = 2500$ A/m in the NO strips. A frequency of 50 Hz was used for both GO and NO strips.

4 Organisation

4.1 *Pilot Laboratory*

Pilot laboratory:

Czech Metrology Institute
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4.2 *Participants*

The following laboratories participated in the comparison:

Acronym	Laboratory	Country	Contact
INRIM	Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica	Italy	Massimo Pasquale m.pasquale@inrim.it Carlo Appino c.appino@inrim.it
PTB	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt	Germany	Franziska Weickert franziska.weickert@ptb.de Korbinian Pfner korbinian.pfner@ptb.de
CMI	Czech Metrology Institute	Czech Republic	Michal Ulvr mulvr@cmi.cz

NPL	National Physical Laboratory	United Kingdom	Stuart Harmon stuart.harmon@npl.co.uk Daniel Brunt daniel.brunt@npl.co.uk
UNOTT	University of Nottingham	United Kingdom	Gaurang Vakil Gaurang.Vakil@nottingham.ac.uk Ram Ramanathan Mathavan Jeyabalan Ram.Ramanathan@nottingham.ac.uk

4.3 *Comparison schedule*

The comparison was carried out by a circulation scheme. The organization of the comparison follows: 1. INRIM, 2. PTB, 3. CMI, 4. NPL, 5. UNOTT and then the samples was returned to INRIM.

It was expected that each participant covers the freight charges from his location to the next on the list. Each participant was responsible for insurance of the samples from arrival in their laboratory until arrival in the subsequent laboratory.

The transport of the travelling standards was arranged by door-to-door parcel service.

5 Measurement instructions

5.1 *Measurements of the samples*

Each participant performed the following measurements using their standard equipment and measurement procedure. The specific total losses were measured stepwise from the lowest to the highest peak polarization value J_m given below at given frequencies. The measuring temperature was 23 ± 1 °C. If not, an appropriate correcting of the coefficient was applied.

Parameters for the Epstein sample NO 0.2	
frequency (Hz)	specific total power loss at J_m
50	1 T, 1.4 T, 1.5 T
100	1 T, 1.4 T, 1.5 T
200	1 T, 1.4 T
400	1 T, 1.4 T

Parameters for the Epstein sample NO 0.3	
frequency (Hz)	specific total power loss at J_m
50	1 T, 1.25 T, 1.5 T
100	1 T, 1.25 T, 1.5 T
200	1 T, 1.25 T, 1.5 T
400	1 T, 1.25 T
1000	0.5 T, 1 T, 1.25 T
2000	0.5 T
5000	0.1 T, 0.2 T, 0.35 T
10000	0.1 T, 0.15 T

Parameters for the Epstein GO samples	
frequency (Hz)	specific total power loss at J_m
50	1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 1.8 T
100	1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 1.8 T
200	1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 1.8 T
400	1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 1.8 T
1000	0.5 T, 1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 1.8 T

Parameters for the Epstein sample FeCo 0.2	
frequency (Hz)	specific total power loss at J_m
50	0.5 T, 1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 2 T
100	0.5 T, 1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 2 T
200	0.5 T, 1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 2 T
400	0.5 T, 1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T, 2 T
1000	0.5 T, 1 T, 1.5 T, 1.7 T
2000	0.5 T
10000	0.1 T, 0.15 T

6 Measurement results

6.1 Calculation of the reference value and its uncertainty

For all measurements of total losses and $J_m(H_m)$ measurements, the evaluation of this comparison was performed following procedure B in [2]. The Mandel-Paule (M-P) mean [3] was chosen for the analysis of the data. On its basis the following characteristics were calculated:

- the modified reduced observed chi-squared value by the formula:

$$\tilde{\chi}_{obs} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(x_i - x_{ref})^2}{u_i^2 + s^2}} \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of participants, x_i is the results of the total losses of the i -th participant of the comparisons and u_i is the declared standard uncertainty of the i -th participant of the comparison for coverage factor $k = 1$ (68%). The value of the unexplained variance s^2 is chosen such that chi-squared value < 1 .

- the reference value of total losses x_{ref} by the formula:

$$x_{ref} = u^2(x_{ref}) \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{x_i}{u_i^2 + s^2} \quad (2)$$

- standard uncertainty of the reference value of total losses $u(x_{ref})$ by the formula:

$$u(x_{ref}) = \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{u_i^2 + s^2} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (3)$$

- the degree of equivalence of the measurement standard d_i by the formula (4) with a corresponding uncertainty by the formulas (5), (6):

$$d_i = x_i - x_{ref} \quad (4)$$

$$u(d_i) = \sqrt{u^2(x_i) + u^2(x_{ref})} \quad (5)$$

$$E_n = \frac{|d_i|}{2u(d_i)}, \quad (6)$$

where d_i is degree of equivalence and $u(d_i)$ is the standard uncertainty of the degree of equivalence.

The declared uncertainties are judged as confirmed if equation $E_n < 1$ is satisfied, that is a confirmation of the relevant rows from CMC.

The maximal value of the expanded uncertainty of the reference value $U(x_{ref})$ ($k = 2$) was chosen as 3 % for frequencies up to 400 Hz and 5 % for frequencies above 400 Hz except FeCo sample, where the maximal value of the expanded uncertainty of the reference value was chosen as 5 % for all frequencies

6.2 Evaluation of comparison results

Parameters of measured samples:

Sample	Density (kg/m ³)	Cross section (× 10 ⁻⁵ m ²)	Weight (kg)	Number of strips, N_s (-)	Nominal length (m)
Laser scribed GO 0.2	7650	3.3105	0.30924	24	0.305
		2.2073	0.20618	16	
		1.6545	0.15455	12	
GO 0.18	7650	2.61590	0.25640	20	0.320
		2.09280	0.20504	16	
NO 0.3	7600	2.64974	0.24140	12	0.300
GO 0.3	7650	4.2840	0.39331	20	0.300
NO 0.2	7650	2.89547	0.26576	20	0.300
		1.73397	0.15917	12	
FeCo 0.2	8120	3.5662	0.34755	24	0.300
		1.7834	0.1736	12	

6.2.1 Total losses results

Results of the NO 0.3 sample

N_s	Losses	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Lab5		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
		X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$		
1-12	$P_{1,0/50}$	0.903	0.25	0.904	0.18	0.903	0.70	0.904	0.325	0.904	0.35	0.9037	0.0011
	$P_{1,4/50}$	1.826	0.25	1.837	0.24	1.830	0.90	1.839	0.375	1.850	0.4	1.8365	0.0048
	$P_{1,5/50}$	2.158	0.40	2.173	0.27	2.160	0.90	2.174	0.375	2.172	0.4	2.1698	0.0037
	$P_{1,0/100}$	2.099	0.25	2.112	0.18	2.090	0.70	2.107	0.325	2.109	0.35	2.1055	0.0047
	$P_{1,4/100}$	4.219	0.25	4.283	0.26	4.230	0.90	4.285	0.375	4.302	0.35	4.2659	0.0218
	$P_{1,5/100}$	4.964	0.25	5.075	0.26	4.990	0.90	5.068	0.375	5.033	0.4	5.0278	0.0309
	$P_{1,0/200}$	5.232	0.30	5.272	0.18	5.220	0.70	5.235	0.20	5.277	0.35	5.251	0.012
	$P_{1,4/200}$	10.552	0.60	10.72	0.24	10.530	0.90	10.56	0.30	10.753	0.40	10.635	0.048
	$P_{1,0/400}$	13.959	0.65	14.17	0.20	14.100	0.90	14.09	0.20	14.217	0.3	14.127	0.040
	$P_{1,4/400}$	28.462	0.65	×	×	28.88	0.9	28.83	0.28	29.480	0.38	28.74	0.12

N_s	Losses	d_i					$u(d_i)$					E_n				
		Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5
1-12	$P_{1,0/50}$	-0.0007	0.0003	-0.0011	0.0003	0.0003	0.003	0.002	0.006	0.003	0.003	0.141	0.072	0.084	0.046	0.043
	$P_{1,4/50}$	-0.0105	0.0007	-0.0065	0.0025	0.0135	0.007	0.006	0.017	0.008	0.009	0.798	0.052	0.190	0.147	0.765
	$P_{1,5/50}$	-0.0118	0.0033	-0.0098	0.0042	0.0022	0.009	0.007	0.020	0.009	0.009	0.629	0.235	0.248	0.233	0.115
	$P_{1,0/100}$	-0.0065	0.0064	-0.0155	0.0015	0.0035	0.007	0.006	0.015	0.008	0.009	0.457	0.531	0.503	0.093	0.202
	$P_{1,4/100}$	-0.0469	0.0171	-0.0359	0.0191	0.0361	0.024	0.024	0.044	0.027	0.026	0.969	0.349	0.410	0.352	0.681
	$P_{1,5/100}$	-0.0638	0.0472	-0.0378	0.0402	0.0052	0.033	0.034	0.054	0.036	0.037	0.959	0.703	0.347	0.555	0.071
	$P_{1,0/200}$	-0.0189	0.0211	-0.0309	-0.0159	0.0261	0.019	0.015	0.038	0.016	0.022	0.485	0.705	0.403	0.510	0.599
	$P_{1,4/200}$	-0.0829	0.0851	-0.1049	-0.0749	0.1181	0.080	0.055	0.106	0.058	0.065	0.520	0.777	0.493	0.647	0.912
	$P_{1,0/400}$	-0.1683	0.0417	-0.0273	-0.0373	0.0897	0.099	0.049	0.133	0.049	0.059	0.848	0.425	0.103	0.381	0.767
	$P_{1,4/400}$	-0.2768	×	0.1412	0.0912	×	0.221	×	0.287	0.144	×	0.627	×	0.246	0.316	×

Results of the GO 0.18 sample

N_s	Losses	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Lab5		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)	
		X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			
1-20	$P_{1,0/50}$	0.256	0.25	0.2369	0.21	0.237	0.50	0.244	0.33	0.2485	0.35	0.2393	0.0026	
	$P_{1,5/50}$	0.549	0.25	0.5322	0.21	0.527	0.50	0.540	0.33	0.5519	0.35	0.5334	0.0036	
	$P_{1,7/50}$	0.700	0.25	0.7243	0.28	0.712	0.70	0.732	0.38	0.7539	0.4	0.7235	0.0055	
	$P_{1,8/50}$	0.929	0.25	0.928	0.55	0.904	1.00	0.931	0.55	0.9935	0.4	0.9248	0.0057	
	$P_{1,0/100}$	0.691	0.25	0.6473	0.20	0.644	0.50	0.676	0.33	0.6741	0.35	0.6605	0.009	
	$P_{1,5/100}$	1.575	0.25	1.4672	0.20	1.450	0.50	1.500	0.33	1.5164	0.4	1.483	0.018	
	$P_{1,7/100}$	2.026	0.25	1.969	0.26	1.935	0.70	1.993	0.35	2.0338	0.4	1.967	0.017	
	$P_{1,8/100}$	2.452	0.25	2.470	0.52	2.411	1.00	2.470	0.50	2.6298	0.45	2.455	0.013	
	$P_{1,0/200}$	1.896	0.25	1.889	0.20	1.887	0.50	1.940	0.33	1.9120	0.35	1.8960	0.006	
	$P_{1,5/200}$	4.315	0.25	4.307	0.20	4.309	0.50	4.312	0.23	4.3940	0.35	4.3106	0.0054	
	$P_{1,7/200}$	5.637	0.25	5.667	0.23	5.639	0.70	5.640	0.23	5.8130	0.4	5.648	0.0093	
	$P_{1,8/200}$	6.741	0.25	6.811	0.42	6.700	1.00	6.74	0.38	7.1330	0.45	6.755	0.025	
	1-16	$P_{1,0/400}$	5.857	0.30	5.839	0.20	5.902	0.50	5.997	0.20	5.8790	0.35	5.862	0.014
		$P_{1,5/400}$	13.384	0.30	13.40	0.18	13.438	0.50	13.30	0.20	13.5930	0.4	13.42	0.070
$P_{1,7/400}$		17.039	0.30	17.11	0.21	17.131	0.70	16.99	0.20	17.3390	0.4	17.053	0.036	
$P_{1,8/400}$		19.463	0.30	19.54	0.26	19.537	1.00	19.41	0.28	20.1700	0.4	19.475	0.038	
$P_{1,0/1000}$		27.105	0.50	27.13	0.21	27.445	0.50	27.30	0.20	27.1500	0.45	27.22	0.062	

N_s	Losses	d_i					$u(d_i)$					E_n				
		Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5
1-20	$P_{1,0/50}$	×	-0.0024	-0.0024	0.0047	×	×	0.003	0.003	0.003	×	×	0.449	0.406	0.857	×
	$P_{1,5/50}$	×	-0.0012	-0.0059	0.0066	×	×	0.004	0.004	0.004	×	×	0.156	0.656	0.819	×
	$P_{1,7/50}$	×	0.0008	-0.0111	0.0085	×	×	0.006	0.007	0.006	×	×	0.066	0.744	0.685	×
	$P_{1,8/50}$	0.0042	0.0032	-0.0208	0.0062	×	0.006	0.008	0.011	0.008	×	0.342	0.210	0.975	0.406	×
	$P_{1,0/100}$	×	-0.0132	-0.0160	0.0155	0.0136	×	0.009	0.010	0.009	0.009	×	0.719	0.832	0.830	0.725
	$P_{1,5/100}$	×	-0.0161	-0.0338	0.0167	0.0331	×	0.018	0.019	0.018	0.019	×	0.450	0.882	0.453	0.883
	$P_{1,7/100}$	×	0.0020	-0.0325	0.0260	×	×	0.018	0.022	0.018	×	×	0.056	0.749	0.707	×
	$P_{1,8/100}$	-0.0030	0.0150	-0.0436	0.0150	×	0.014	0.018	0.027	0.018	×	0.105	0.411	0.796	0.419	×
	$P_{1,0/200}$	0.0000	-0.0070	-0.0092	×	0.0160	0.008	0.007	0.011	×	0.009	0.002	0.504	0.413	×	0.898
	$P_{1,5/200}$	0.0044	-0.0036	-0.0019	0.0014	×	0.012	0.010	0.022	0.011	×	0.182	0.178	0.042	0.063	×
	$P_{1,7/200}$	-0.0108	0.0192	-0.0086	-0.0078	×	0.017	0.016	0.041	0.016	×	0.319	0.599	0.106	0.247	×
	$P_{1,8/200}$	-0.0140	0.0560	-0.0546	-0.0150	×	0.030	0.038	0.072	0.036	×	0.231	0.732	0.381	0.210	×
1-16	$P_{1,0/400}$	-0.0054	-0.0234	0.0397	×	0.0166	0.022	0.018	0.033	×	0.025	0.122	0.649	0.610	×	0.335
	$P_{1,5/400}$	-0.0351	-0.0221	0.0192	-0.1191	0.1739	0.081	0.074	0.097	0.075	0.089	0.217	0.149	0.099	0.795	0.981
	$P_{1,7/400}$	-0.0139	0.0581	0.0778	-0.0629	×	0.062	0.051	0.125	0.049	×	0.112	0.575	0.311	0.640	×
	$P_{1,8/400}$	-0.0118	0.0642	0.0625	-0.0648	×	0.070	0.064	0.199	0.066	×	0.085	0.505	0.157	0.494	×
	$P_{1,0/1000}$	-0.1154	-0.0934	0.2251	0.0796	-0.0704	0.149	0.084	0.150	0.082	0.137	0.387	0.556	0.748	0.483	0.257

Results of the GO 0.3 sample

N_s	Losses	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Lab5		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
		X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$		
1-20	$P_{1,0/50}$	0.343	0.50	0.338	0.20	0.338	0.50	0.3419	0.33	0.345	0.3	0.3411	0.0015
	$P_{1,5/50}$	0.747	0.25	0.752	0.20	0.749	0.50	0.747	0.33	0.766	0.35	0.7490	0.0015
	$P_{1,7/50}$	1.011	0.40	1.004	0.24	0.997	0.70	0.994	0.35	1.024	0.4	1.006	0.0092
	$P_{1,8/50}$	1.230	0.40	1.234	0.44	1.231	1.00	1.227	0.48	1.291	0.4	1.230	0.0030
	$P_{1,0/100}$	1.013	0.25	1.021	0.19	1.006	0.50	1.008	0.20	1.017	0.5	1.0130	0.0047
	$P_{1,5/100}$	2.232	0.25	2.259	0.20	2.239	0.50	2.240	0.20	2.275	0.35	2.249	0.0138
	$P_{1,7/100}$	2.935	0.25	2.940	0.22	2.907	0.70	2.909	0.23	2.982	0.35	2.925	0.0089
	$P_{1,8/100}$	3.430	0.25	3.466	0.36	3.439	1.00	3.434	0.33	3.571	0.4	3.441	0.0090
	$P_{1,0/200}$	3.100	0.25	3.103	0.19	3.122	0.50	3.119	0.20	3.127	0.4	3.111	0.0053
	$P_{1,5/200}$	6.852	0.25	6.838	0.22	6.857	0.50	6.835	0.20	6.927	0.4	6.859	0.020
	$P_{1,7/200}$	8.897	0.25	8.948	0.23	8.879	0.70	8.90	0.23	9.040	0.45	8.914	0.014
	$P_{1,8/200}$	10.356	0.25	10.46	0.32	10.393	1.00	10.40	0.30	10.760	0.45	10.402	0.026
	$P_{1,0/400}$	9.623	1.00	9.827	0.20	9.786	0.50	9.78	0.20	9.812	0.35	9.793	0.024
	$P_{1,5/400}$	21.694	0.75	21.95	0.20	21.969	0.50	21.82	0.20	22.180	0.35	21.88	0.055
	$P_{1,7/400}$	29.030	0.50	29.44	0.24	29.330	0.70	29.23	0.23	29.830	0.40	29.27	0.090
	$P_{1,8/400}$	34.262	0.50	34.69	0.32	34.417	1.00	34.42	0.28	35.530	0.40	34.48	0.103
	$P_{0,5/1000}$	12.984	0.80	12.71	0.22	12.576	0.80	12.97	0.20	12.797	0.50	12.81	0.08
	$P_{1,0/1000}$	45.120	0.60	45.34	0.22	45.398	0.80	45.29	0.20	45.830	0.40	45.40	0.12

N_s	Losses	d_i					$u(d_i)$					E_n				
		Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5
1-20	$P_{1,0/50}$	0.0019	-0.0032	-0.0028	0.0008	0.0034	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.419	0.997	0.617	0.214	0.948
	$P_{1,5/50}$	-0.0020	0.0030	0.0000	-0.0020	×	0.002	0.002	0.004	0.003	×	0.423	0.703	0.003	0.355	×
	$P_{1,7/50}$	0.0050	-0.0022	-0.0093	-0.0120	0.0180	0.010	0.009	0.012	0.010	0.010	0.250	0.115	0.405	0.612	0.898
	$P_{1,8/50}$	-0.0004	0.0032	0.0008	-0.0034	×	0.006	0.006	0.013	0.007	×	0.033	0.260	0.033	0.258	×
	$P_{1,0/100}$	-0.0005	0.0083	-0.0072	-0.0050	0.0040	0.005	0.005	0.007	0.005	0.007	0.051	0.806	0.521	0.490	0.285
	$P_{1,5/100}$	-0.0171	0.0102	-0.0100	-0.0091	0.0259	0.015	0.015	0.018	0.014	0.016	0.575	0.352	0.281	0.314	0.814
	$P_{1,7/100}$	0.0097	0.0148	-0.0188	-0.0163	×	0.012	0.011	0.022	0.011	×	0.420	0.673	0.423	0.738	×
	$P_{1,8/100}$	-0.0114	0.0246	-0.0024	-0.0074	×	0.012	0.015	0.036	0.014	×	0.460	0.799	0.034	0.259	×
	$P_{1,0/200}$	-0.0115	-0.0083	0.0102	0.0075	0.0155	0.009	0.008	0.016	0.008	0.014	0.612	0.523	0.311	0.459	0.571
	$P_{1,5/200}$	-0.0067	-0.0207	-0.0020	-0.0237	0.0683	0.027	0.025	0.040	0.025	0.034	0.126	0.409	0.025	0.484	0.994
	$P_{1,7/200}$	-0.0166	0.0344	-0.0344	-0.0136	×	0.027	0.025	0.064	0.025	×	0.312	0.684	0.269	0.275	×
	$P_{1,8/200}$	-0.0458	0.0602	-0.0089	-0.0018	×	0.037	0.042	0.107	0.041	×	0.625	0.712	0.041	0.022	×
	$P_{1,0/400}$	-0.1700	0.0340	-0.0069	-0.0130	0.0190	0.099	0.031	0.055	0.031	0.042	0.857	0.545	0.063	0.209	0.226
	$P_{1,5/400}$	-0.1856	0.0664	0.0898	-0.0596	×	0.172	0.071	0.123	0.071	×	0.540	0.469	0.365	0.423	×
	$P_{1,7/400}$	-0.2432	0.1688	0.0571	-0.0432	×	0.171	0.114	0.224	0.112	×	0.712	0.737	0.127	0.194	×
	$P_{1,8/400}$	-0.2134	0.2146	-0.0581	-0.0554	×	0.200	0.152	0.359	0.140	×	0.534	0.708	0.081	0.198	×
	$P_{0,5/1000}$	0.1730	-0.0990	-0.2351	0.1590	-0.0140	0.130	0.083	0.127	0.082	0.101	0.666	0.599	0.924	0.969	0.069
	$P_{1,0/1000}$	-0.2782	-0.0582	-0.0001	-0.1082	0.4318	0.296	0.156	0.383	0.151	0.219	0.469	0.186	0.000	0.359	0.984

Results of the NO 0.2 sample

N_s	Losses	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Lab5		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
		X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$		
1-20	$P_{1,0/50}$	0.961	0.25	0.961	0.17	0.962	0.70	0.959	0.35	0.965	0.35	0.9612	0.0012
	$P_{1,25/50}$	1.469	0.25	1.475	0.22	1.474	0.70	1.471	0.38	1.489	0.45	1.475	0.004
	$P_{1,5/50}$	2.237	0.25	2.268	0.27	2.251	0.90	2.247	0.38	2.287	0.45	2.261	0.011
	$P_{1,0/100}$	2.098	0.25	2.102	0.19	2.099	0.70	2.092	0.35	1.906	0.35	2.099	0.0029
	$P_{1,25/100}$	3.195	0.25	3.226	0.22	3.223	0.70	3.205	0.35	3.256	0.35	3.221	0.015
	$P_{1,5/100}$	4.854	0.25	4.978	0.27	4.911	0.90	4.909	0.38	4.979	0.4	4.931	0.037
	$P_{1,0/200}$	4.791	0.30	4.829	0.19	4.809	0.70	4.814	0.33	4.863	0.5	4.820	0.011
	$P_{1,25/200}$	7.303	0.50	7.407	0.22	7.371	0.70	7.40	0.35	7.484	0.4	7.40	0.032
	$P_{1,5/200}$	11.065	0.80	11.48	0.27	11.248	0.90	11.39	0.35	11.425	0.4	11.32	0.10
1-12	$P_{1,0/400}$	11.43	0.4	11.71	1.09	11.635	0.7	11.70	0.325	11.661	0.5	11.62	0.087
	$P_{1,25/400}$	17.52	0.4	18.19	4.1	17.912	0.7	17.92	0.325	17.996	0.40	17.85	0.15
	$P_{0,5/1000}$	12.089	0.6	12.35	0.64	12.205	0.7	12.22	0.20	12.287	0.40	12.231	0.041
	$P_{1,0/1000}$	41.33	0.8	42.67	0.71	42.343	0.8	41.92	0.20	42.530	0.40	42.32	0.21
	$P_{1,25/1000}$	63.98	0.8	67.2	3.39	65.865	0.9	65.01	0.20	66.200	0.40	65.67	0.38
	$P_{0,5/2000}$	33.1	0.8	×	×	33.920	0.7	33.68	0.20	33.908	0.40	33.68	0.17
1-12	$P_{0,1/5000}$	×	×	×	×	6.603	0.9	6.884	0.20	6.539	0.45	6.68	0.11
	$P_{0,2/5000}$	×	×	×	×	25.628	0.9	26.06	0.20	25.620	0.50	25.81	0.16
	$P_{0,35/5000}$	×	×	×	×	72.046	0.9	71.75	0.20	72.620	0.50	72.06	0.28
	$P_{0,1/10000}$	×	×	×	×	20.931	1	21.68	0.20	20.920	0.45	21.20	0.27
	$P_{0,15/10000}$	×	×	×	×	45.383	1	46.19	0.20	45.810	0.50	45.93	0.22

N_s	Losses	d_i					$u(d_i)$					E_n				
		Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5
1-20	P _{1,0/50}	-0.0002	-0.0002	0.0003	-0.0022	0.0038	0.003	0.002	0.007	0.004	0.004	0.047	0.062	0.024	0.317	0.525
	P _{1,25/50}	-0.0057	0.0000	-0.0011	-0.0037	0.0143	0.005	0.005	0.011	0.007	0.008	0.550	0.002	0.049	0.278	0.940
	P _{1,5/50}	-0.0239	0.0068	-0.0096	-0.0139	0.0261	0.013	0.013	0.023	0.014	0.015	0.946	0.265	0.207	0.492	0.854
	P _{1,0/100}	-0.0013	0.0029	-0.0001	-0.0073	×	0.006	0.005	0.015	0.008	×	0.107	0.297	0.005	0.463	×
	P _{1,25/100}	-0.0255	0.0056	0.0020	-0.0155	0.0355	0.017	0.016	0.027	0.018	0.018	0.771	0.172	0.036	0.424	0.961
	P _{1,5/100}	-0.0771	0.0469	-0.0204	-0.0221	0.0479	0.039	0.039	0.058	0.041	0.042	0.990	0.595	0.177	0.268	0.569
	P _{1,0/200}	-0.0285	0.0094	-0.0101	-0.0055	0.0435	0.018	0.015	0.036	0.019	0.027	0.781	0.322	0.142	0.144	0.811
	P _{1,25/200}	-0.0930	0.0110	-0.0254	0.0040	0.0880	0.049	0.036	0.061	0.042	0.044	0.952	0.151	0.208	0.048	0.996
	P _{1,5/200}	-0.2535	0.1625	-0.0706	0.0715	0.1065	0.131	0.101	0.140	0.104	0.107	0.968	0.801	0.252	0.342	0.498
1-12	P _{1,0/400}	-0.1918	0.0882	0.0136	0.0782	0.0392	0.098	0.154	0.119	0.095	0.105	0.977	0.286	0.057	0.412	0.187
	P _{1,25/400}	-0.3282	0.3418	0.0641	0.0718	0.1478	0.168	0.761	0.198	0.164	0.169	0.975	0.225	0.162	0.219	0.437
	P _{0,5/1000}	-0.1420	0.1160	-0.0255	-0.0110	0.0560	0.083	0.089	0.095	0.048	0.064	0.851	0.651	0.135	0.115	0.437
	P _{1,0/1000}	×	0.3488	0.0218	-0.4012	0.2088	×	0.367	0.397	0.224	0.268	×	0.475	0.027	0.896	0.389
	P _{1,25/1000}	×	1.5306	0.1956	-0.6594	0.5306	×	2.310	0.704	0.402	0.463	×	0.331	0.139	0.821	0.573
	P _{0,5/2000}	-0.5837	×	0.2363	-0.0037	0.2243	0.317	×	0.295	0.187	0.221	0.920	×	0.401	0.010	0.508
1-12	P _{0,1/5000}	×	×	-0.0753	0.2057	-0.1393	×	×	0.127	0.113	0.116	×	×	0.297	0.912	0.602
	P _{0,2/5000}	×	×	-0.1803	0.2517	-0.1883	×	×	0.281	0.168	0.205	×	×	0.321	0.748	0.460
	P _{0,35/5000}	×	×	-0.0147	-0.3107	0.5593	×	×	0.706	0.315	0.458	×	×	0.010	0.494	0.610
	P _{0,1/10000}	×	×	-0.2640	0.4850	-0.2750	×	×	0.342	0.274	0.286	×	×	0.386	0.886	0.480
	P _{0,15/10000}	×	×	-0.5445	0.2625	-0.1175	×	×	0.505	0.239	0.318	×	×	0.540	0.549	0.185

Results of the Laser scribed GO 0.2 sample

N_s	Losses	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Lab5		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
		X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$								
1-24	P _{1,0/50}	0.267	0.40	0.2636	0.22	0.267	0.50	0.2659	0.33	0.2721	0.35	0.2657	0.0011
	P _{1,5/50}	0.578	0.25	0.5785	0.21	0.583	0.50	0.580	0.33	0.5950	0.35	0.5790	0.0008
	P _{1,7/50}	0.791	0.25	0.7885	0.30	0.795	0.70	0.789	0.38	0.8170	0.4	0.7900	0.0017
	P _{1,8/50}	1.027	0.25	1.016	0.60	1.029	1.00	1.015	0.55	1.0930	0.45	1.022	0.0037
	P _{1,0/100}	0.726	0.25	0.7258	0.29	0.739	0.50	0.739	0.33	0.7405	0.45	0.7338	0.0038
	P _{1,5/100}	1.602	0.25	1.605	0.20	1.611	0.50	1.618	0.33	1.6515	0.45	1.6081	0.0039
	P _{1,7/100}	2.126	0.25	2.153	0.26	2.139	0.70	2.151	0.35	2.2235	0.35	2.142	0.0072
	P _{1,8/100}	2.710	0.40	2.705	0.55	2.682	1.00	2.693	0.50	2.8963	0.35	2.699	0.017
1-16	P _{1,0/200}	2.150	0.25	×	×	2.150	0.50	2.167	0.33	2.1686	0.3	2.1594	0.0054
	P _{1,5/200}	4.878	0.25	×	×	4.779	0.50	4.789	0.33	4.8395	0.3	4.823	0.031
	P _{1,7/200}	6.232	0.25	×	×	6.237	0.70	6.256	0.33	6.3878	0.4	6.241	0.012
	P _{1,8/200}	7.442	0.25	×	×	7.470	1.00	7.52	0.45	7.926	0.45	7.471	0.026
1-12	P _{1,0/400}	6.642	0.30	×	×	6.664	0.50	6.636	0.20	6.632	0.40	6.639	0.0098
	P _{1,5/400}	14.953	0.30	×	×	14.869	0.50	14.81	0.20	14.890	0.40	14.875	0.035
	P _{1,7/400}	18.985	0.30	×	×	18.961	0.70	18.98	0.20	19.150	0.40	18.980	0.031
	P _{1,8/400}	21.890	0.30	×	×	21.954	1.00	21.96	0.28	22.710	0.45	21.929	0.044
	P _{1,0/1000}	30.178	0.5	×	×	30.602	0.50	30.38	0.20	30.410	0.35	30.39	0.075
	P _{1,5/1000}	65.28	0.5	×	×	66.280	0.50	65.81	0.20	66.400	0.35	65.95	0.25
	P _{1,7/1000}	85.25	0.5	×	×	85.512	0.70	85.3	0.20	86.970	0.40	85.31	0.15
	P _{1,8/1000}	98.88	0.5	×	×	99.246	1.00	98.9	0.28	102.860	0.45	98.92	0.24

N_s	Losses	d_i					$u(d_i)$					E_n				
		Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5
1-24	P _{1,0/50}	0.0013	-0.0021	0.0010	0.0002	×	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.001	×	0.426	0.828	0.298	0.075	×
	P _{1,5/50}	-0.0008	-0.0005	0.0038	0.0010	×	0.002	0.001	0.003	0.002	×	0.244	0.175	0.635	0.242	×
	P _{1,7/50}	0.0008	-0.0015	0.0050	-0.0010	×	0.003	0.003	0.006	0.003	×	0.147	0.261	0.426	0.150	×
	P _{1,8/50}	0.0051	-0.0056	0.0072	-0.0069	×	0.005	0.007	0.011	0.007	×	0.561	0.396	0.327	0.519	×
	P _{1,0/100}	-0.0078	-0.0080	0.0052	0.0052	0.0067	0.004	0.004	0.005	0.004	0.005	0.925	0.919	0.489	0.586	0.669
	P _{1,5/100}	-0.0062	-0.0031	0.0033	0.0099	×	0.006	0.005	0.009	0.007	×	0.559	0.311	0.184	0.755	×
	P _{1,7/100}	-0.0166	0.0107	-0.0029	0.0088	×	0.009	0.009	0.017	0.010	×	0.928	0.584	0.087	0.420	×
P _{1,8/100}	0.0109	0.0062	-0.0173	-0.0061	×	0.020	0.023	0.032	0.022	×	0.270	0.137	0.271	0.140	×	
1-16	P _{1,0/200}	-0.0093	×	-0.0095	0.0076	0.0092	0.008	×	0.012	0.009	0.008	0.613	×	0.394	0.428	0.544
	P _{1,5/200}	0.0553	×	-0.0433	-0.0337	0.0168	0.033	×	0.039	0.035	0.034	0.826	×	0.552	0.484	0.244
	P _{1,7/200}	-0.0086	×	-0.0038	0.0154	×	0.020	×	0.045	0.024	×	0.219	×	0.042	0.327	×
	P _{1,8/200}	-0.0294	×	-0.0011	0.0486	×	0.032	×	0.079	0.043	×	0.456	×	0.007	0.567	×
1-12	P _{1,0/400}	0.0025	×	0.0251	-0.0033	-0.0073	0.022	×	0.035	0.016	0.028	0.057	×	0.361	0.099	0.129
	P _{1,5/400}	0.0783	×	-0.0057	-0.0647	0.0153	0.057	×	0.082	0.046	0.069	0.686	×	0.035	0.704	0.110
	P _{1,7/400}	0.0046	×	-0.0198	-0.0004	×	0.065	×	0.136	0.049	×	0.035	×	0.073	0.004	×
	P _{1,8/400}	-0.0390	×	0.0254	0.0310	×	0.079	×	0.224	0.074	×	0.247	×	0.057	0.208	×
	P _{1,0/1000}	-0.2124	×	0.2111	-0.0104	0.0196	0.168	×	0.170	0.096	0.130	0.631	×	0.620	0.054	0.076
	P _{1,5/1000}	-0.6710	×	0.3294	-0.1410	0.4490	0.409	×	0.413	0.279	0.338	0.821	×	0.399	0.253	0.663
	P _{1,7/1000}	-0.0574	×	0.2047	-0.0074	×	0.453	×	0.618	0.229	×	0.063	×	0.166	0.016	×
P _{1,8/1000}	-0.0348	×	0.3310	-0.0148	×	0.547	×	1.020	0.363	×	0.032	×	0.162	0.020	×	

Additional results of the Laser scribed GO 0.2 sample (200 Hz – 1000 Hz) with Lab2 measurements

N_s	Losses	Lab1		Lab2*		Lab3		Lab4		Lab5		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
		X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$		
1-16	P _{1,0/200}	2.150	0.25	2.149	0.13	2.150	0.50	2.167	0.33	2.1686	0.3	2.1564	0.0045
	P _{1,5/200}	4.878	0.25	4.795	0.18	4.779	0.50	4.789	0.33	4.8395	0.3	4.817	0.032
	P _{1,7/200}	6.232	0.25	6.288	0.16	6.237	0.70	6.256	0.33	6.3878	0.4	6.257	0.018
	P _{1,8/200}	7.442	0.25	7.538	0.28	7.470	1.00	7.52	0.45	7.926	0.45	7.495	0.030
1-12	P _{1,0/400}	6.642	0.30	6.661	0.13	6.664	0.50	6.636	0.20	6.632	0.40	6.651	0.0071
	P _{1,5/400}	14.953	0.30	14.77	0.14	14.869	0.50	14.81	0.20	14.890	0.40	14.850	0.037
	P _{1,7/400}	18.985	0.30	18.9	0.13	18.961	0.70	18.98	0.20	19.150	0.40	18.938	0.023
	P _{1,8/400}	21.890	0.30	21.82	0.21	21.954	1.00	21.96	0.28	22.710	0.45	21.881	0.036
	P _{1,0/1000}	30.178	0.5	30.08	0.14	30.602	0.50	30.38	0.20	30.410	0.35	30.32	0.11
	P _{1,5/1000}	65.28	0.5	65.74	0.17	66.280	0.50	65.81	0.20	66.400	0.35	65.90	0.19
	P _{1,7/1000}	85.25	0.5	85.22	0.36	85.512	0.70	85.3	0.20	86.970	0.40	85.29	0.14
	P _{1,8/1000}	98.88	0.5	99.3	1.06	99.246	1.00	98.9	0.28	102.860	0.45	98.93	0.23

*Lab2 measured the Laser Scribed GO 0.2 sample with N1-24 in the frequency range of 200 Hz to 1000 Hz

N_s	Losses	d_i					$u(d_i)$					E_n				
		Lab1	Lab2*	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2*	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2*	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5
1-16	P _{1,0/200}	-0.0063	-0.0076	-0.0064	0.0106	0.0122	0.007	0.005	0.012	0.008	0.008	0.445	0.712	0.275	0.635	0.771
	P _{1,5/200}	0.0613	-0.0217	-0.0374	-0.0277	0.0228	0.034	0.033	0.040	0.036	0.035	0.893	0.327	0.467	0.389	0.323
	P _{1,7/200}	-0.0254	0.0306	-0.0206	-0.0014	x	0.024	0.021	0.047	0.027	x	0.529	0.735	0.218	0.025	x
	P _{1,8/200}	-0.0528	0.0432	-0.0246	0.0252	x	0.036	0.037	0.081	0.045	x	0.743	0.586	0.152	0.277	x
1-12	P _{1,0/400}	-0.0088	0.0104	0.0137	-0.0146	-0.0186	0.021	0.011	0.034	0.015	0.027	0.208	0.470	0.202	0.485	0.339
	P _{1,5/400}	0.1032	-0.0778	0.0193	-0.0398	0.0402	0.058	0.042	0.083	0.048	0.070	0.885	0.920	0.116	0.418	0.286
	P _{1,7/400}	0.0466	-0.0384	0.0221	0.0416	x	0.062	0.035	0.135	0.045	x	0.378	0.555	0.082	0.466	x
	P _{1,8/400}	0.0094	-0.0636	0.0738	0.0794	x	0.075	0.059	0.223	0.070	x	0.063	0.539	0.166	0.563	x
	P _{1,0/1000}	-0.1409	-0.2369	0.2826	0.0611	0.0911	0.189	0.121	0.190	0.129	0.155	0.373	0.982	0.742	0.237	0.293
	P _{1,5/1000}	-0.6176	-0.1576	0.3828	-0.0876	0.5024	0.376	0.216	0.380	0.228	0.298	0.822	0.365	0.504	0.192	0.844
	P _{1,7/1000}	-0.0398	-0.0698	0.2223	0.0102	x	0.448	0.334	0.614	0.219	x	0.044	0.104	0.181	0.023	x
	P _{1,8/1000}	-0.0532	0.3668	0.3127	-0.0332	x	0.545	1.075	1.019	0.359	x	0.049	0.171	0.153	0.046	x

*Lab2 measured the Laser Scribed GO 0.2 sample with N1-24 in the frequency range of 200 Hz to 1000 Hz

Results of the FeCo 0.2 sample

N_s	Losses	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		Lab5		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
		X	$u_x, \%$										
1-24	P _{0,5/50}	0.324	0.50	0.3226	1.56	0.324	1.5	0.3095	0.55	0.3299	0.4	0.3219	0.0064
	P _{1,0/50}	0.853	0.50	0.8611	0.71	0.871	1.50	0.833	0.50	0.8726	0.4	0.8577	0.0120
	P _{1,5/50}	1.525	0.50	1.5625	0.43	1.565	1.00	1.519	0.65	1.5754	0.45	1.5492	0.0237
	P _{1,7/50}	1.896	0.50	1.9121	0.43	1.909	1.00	1.863	0.55	1.9010	0.45	1.8961	0.0273
	P _{2,0/50}	2.365	0.50	2.385	0.40	2.375	1.00	2.324	0.60	2.352	0.45	2.3603	0.0364
	P _{0,5/100}	0.688	0.50	0.6916	1.56	0.709	1.5	0.6738	0.80	0.703	0.35	0.6929	0.0138
	P _{1,0/100}	1.857	0.50	1.905	0.70	1.914	1.50	1.842	0.50	1.917	0.35	1.8857	0.0233
	P _{1,5/100}	3.353	0.50	3.445	0.41	3.434	1.00	3.36	0.50	3.452	0.35	3.4085	0.0369
	P _{1,7/100}	4.186	0.50	4.241	0.43	4.230	1.00	4.137	0.70	4.235	0.45	4.2058	0.0638
	P _{2,0/100}	5.255	0.50	5.327	0.40	5.294	1.00	5.186	0.70	5.269	0.45	5.2663	0.0819
	P _{0,5/200}	1.517	0.50	1.531	1.39	1.606	1.5	1.508	0.325	1.540	0.4	1.5388	0.0276
	P _{1,0/200}	4.320	0.50	4.378	0.67	4.407	1.50	4.256	0.33	4.372	0.40	4.3429	0.0513
	P _{1,5/200}	7.714	0.50	8.057	0.43	8.034	1.00	7.84	0.33	8.052	0.45	7.9379	0.1137
	P _{1,7/200}	9.563	0.50	9.841	0.44	9.750	1.00	9.52	0.33	9.842	0.45	9.7017	0.1102
P _{2,0/200}	12.188	0.50	12.54	0.40	12.510	1.00	12.12	0.35	12.434	0.45	12.3541	0.1205	
P _{0,5/400}	3.467	0.50	3.714	1.56	3.561	2.00	3.504	0.40	3.532	0.35	3.5513	0.0695	
1-12	P _{1,0/400}	9.724	0.50	×	×	9.952	2.00	9.85	0.40	10.008	0.35	9.8714	0.0691
	P _{1,5/400}	19.050	0.50	×	×	19.711	1.00	19.75	0.40	19.967	0.45	19.6185	0.2763
	P _{1,7/400}	24.321	0.50	×	×	24.772	1.00	24.78	0.40	24.919	0.45	24.6962	0.1650
	P _{2,0/400}	32.026	0.50	×	×	32.606	1	32.75	0.40	32.567	0.40	32.4880	0.2004
1-12	P _{0,5/1000}	10.462	0.5	×	×	10.950	1.5	10.92	0.40	10.819	0.40	10.78	0.16

	P _{1.0/1000}	33.519	0.5	×	×	35.239	1.5	35.30	0.40	34.913	0.45	34.7208	0.5181
	P _{1.5/1000}	73.6	0.5	×	×	77.002	1	78.9	0.45	77.430	0.45	77.9139	0.5800
	P _{1.7/1000}	99.1	0.5	×	×	103.504	1	103.9	0.45	103.710	0.35	103.8304	0.1960
	P _{0.5/2000}	×	×	×	×	×	×	28.83	0.40	28.300	0.45	28.5751	0.2911
	P _{0.1/10000}	×	×	×	×	×	×	19.13	0.60	18.720	0.45	18.9311	0.2170
	P _{0.15/10000}	×	×	×	×	×	×	40.56	0.60	39.620	0.42	40.0998	0.5034

N_s	Losses	d_i					$u(d_i)$					E_n				
		Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5
1-24	P _{0.5/50}	0.0021	0.0007	0.0020	-0.0124	0.0080	0.007	0.008	0.008	0.007	0.007	0.155	0.040	0.124	0.936	0.606
	P _{1.0/50}	-0.0047	0.0034	0.0135	-0.0247	0.0149	0.013	0.013	0.018	0.013	0.013	0.184	0.126	0.380	0.970	0.595
	P _{1.5/50}	-0.0242	0.0133	0.0153	-0.0302	0.0262	0.025	0.025	0.028	0.026	0.025	0.487	0.270	0.270	0.589	0.530
	P _{1.7/50}	-0.0001	0.0160	0.0129	-0.0331	0.0049	0.029	0.029	0.033	0.029	0.029	0.002	0.280	0.194	0.567	0.086
	P _{2.0/50}	0.0047	0.0247	0.0151	-0.0363	-0.0079	0.038	0.038	0.043	0.039	0.038	0.062	0.329	0.174	0.466	0.104
	P _{0.5/100}	-0.0049	-0.0013	0.0163	-0.0191	0.0099	0.014	0.018	0.017	0.015	0.014	0.171	0.036	0.468	0.643	0.355
	P _{1.0/100}	-0.0287	0.0194	0.0281	-0.0437	0.0313	0.025	0.027	0.037	0.025	0.024	0.572	0.361	0.379	0.872	0.645
	P _{1.5/100}	-0.0555	0.0368	0.0252	-0.0485	0.0435	0.041	0.039	0.050	0.041	0.039	0.685	0.467	0.250	0.598	0.561
	P _{1.7/100}	-0.0198	0.0351	0.0241	-0.0688	0.0292	0.067	0.066	0.077	0.070	0.067	0.147	0.265	0.157	0.491	0.220
	P _{2.0/100}	-0.0113	0.0606	0.0276	-0.0803	0.0030	0.086	0.085	0.098	0.090	0.085	0.065	0.358	0.141	0.448	0.018
	P _{0.5/200}	-0.0218	-0.0074	0.0668	-0.0308	0.0012	0.029	0.035	0.037	0.028	0.028	0.381	0.106	0.911	0.549	0.021
	P _{1.0/200}	-0.0229	0.0346	0.0638	-0.0869	0.0291	0.056	0.059	0.084	0.053	0.054	0.206	0.293	0.381	0.817	0.268
	P _{1.5/200}	-0.2239	0.1191	0.0962	-0.0979	0.1141	0.120	0.119	0.139	0.117	0.119	0.933	0.501	0.345	0.420	0.478
	P _{1.7/200}	-0.1387	0.1393	0.0486	-0.1817	0.1403	0.120	0.118	0.147	0.115	0.119	0.577	0.588	0.165	0.794	0.590
	P _{2.0/200}	-0.1661	0.1889	0.1563	-0.2341	0.0799	0.135	0.131	0.174	0.128	0.133	0.615	0.724	0.450	0.916	0.301
P _{0.5/400}	-0.0843	0.1626	0.0096	-0.0473	-0.0193	0.072	0.090	0.100	0.071	0.071	0.588	0.898	0.048	0.334	0.137	

1-12	P _{1,0/400}	-0.1474	×	0.0806	-0.0214	0.1366	0.085	×	0.211	0.073	0.078	0.872	×	0.191	0.147	0.881
	P _{1,5/400}	-0.5685	×	0.0924	0.1315	0.3485	0.292	×	0.339	0.279	0.291	0.973	×	0.136	0.236	0.600
	P _{1,7/400}	-0.3752	×	0.0758	0.0838	0.2228	0.205	×	0.298	0.172	0.200	0.915	×	0.127	0.243	0.558
	P _{2,0/400}	×	×	0.1180	0.2620	0.0790	×	×	0.383	0.214	0.239	×	×	0.154	0.612	0.165
1-12	P _{0,5/1000}	-0.3179	×	0.1699	0.1401	0.0391	0.164	×	0.226	0.157	0.162	0.968	×	0.375	0.446	0.121
	P _{1,0/1000}	×	×	0.5184	0.5792	0.1922	×	×	0.740	0.523	0.541	×	×	0.350	0.554	0.177
	P _{1,5/1000}	×	×	-0.9123	0.9861	-0.4839	×	×	0.964	0.608	0.677	×	×	0.473	0.811	0.358
	P _{1,7/1000}	×	×	-0.3267	0.0696	-0.1204	×	×	1.053	0.309	0.413	×	×	0.155	0.113	0.146
	P _{0,5/2000}	×	×	×	0.2549	-0.2751	×	×	×	0.297	0.318	×	×	×	0.429	0.433
	P _{0,1/10000}	×	×	×	0.1989	-0.2111	×	×	×	0.220	0.233	×	×	×	0.451	0.453
	P _{0,15/10000}	×	×	×	0.4602	-0.4798	×	×	×	0.510	0.530	×	×	×	0.451	0.452

Additional results of the FeCo sample (400 Hz – 1000 Hz) with Lab2 measurements

N_s	Losses	Lab1		Lab2*		Lab3		Lab4		Lab5		x_{ref} (W/kg)	$u(x_{ref})$ (W/kg)
		X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$		
N1-12	P _{1,0/400}	9.724	0.50	10.40	0.10	9.952	2.00	9.85	0.40	10.008	0.35	9.8714	0.0691
	P _{1,5/400}	19.050	0.50	19.49	0.10	19.711	1.00	19.75	0.40	19.967	0.45	19.6185	0.2763
	P _{1,7/400}	24.321	0.50	25.13	0.10	24.772	1.00	24.78	0.40	24.919	0.45	24.6962	0.1650
	P _{2,0/400}	32.026	0.50	33.01	0.10	32.606	1	32.75	0.40	32.567	0.40	32.4880	0.2004
	P _{1,0/1000}	33.519	0.5	35.79	0.32	35.239	1.5	35.30	0.40	34.913	0.45	34.7208	0.5181

*Lab2 measured FeCo sample with N1-24 in the frequency range of 400 Hz to 1000 Hz

N_s	Losses	d_i					$u(d_i)$					E_n				
		Lab1	Lab2*	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2*	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5	Lab1	Lab2*	Lab3	Lab4	Lab5
N1-12	P _{1,0/400}	-0.2643	0.4097	-0.0363	-0.1383	0.0197	0.215	0.210	0.289	0.213	0.212	0.614	0.976	0.063	0.324	0.046
	P _{1,5/400}	-0.5412	-0.1032	0.1197	0.1588	0.3758	0.281	0.265	0.329	0.276	0.279	0.964	0.195	0.182	0.288	0.674
	P _{1,7/400}	-0.4696	0.3424	-0.0187	-0.0106	0.1284	0.243	0.212	0.325	0.232	0.238	0.968	0.809	0.029	0.023	0.270
	P _{2,0/400}	×	0.2230	-0.1840	-0.0400	-0.2230	×	0.118	0.345	0.173	0.173	×	0.941	0.266	0.115	0.645
	P _{1,0/1000}	×	0.4549	-0.0958	-0.0351	-0.4221	×	0.236	0.567	0.249	0.259	×	0.966	0.084	0.070	0.816

*Lab2 measured FeCo sample with N1-24 in the frequency range of 400 Hz to 1000 Hz

NO 0.3 sample

GO 0.18 sample

GO 0.3 sample

NO 0.2 sample

Laser scribed GO 0.2

Additional results of the Laser scribed GO 0.2 sample (200 Hz – 1000 Hz)

FeCo 0.2

Additional results of the FeCo sample (400 Hz – 1000 Hz)

6.2.2 $J_m(H_m)$ curve results at 50 Hz

H_m (A/m)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i				$u(d_i)$				E_n			
	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL	CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL	CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL
2500	1.536	0.25	1.5424	0.062	1.546	0.50	1.542	0.28	1.5411	0.0032	-0.005	0.001	0.005	0.001	0.010	0.007	0.017	0.011	0.256	0.097	0.146	0.042

Results of the NO 0.3 sample

H_m (A/m)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i				$u(d_i)$				E_n			
	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL	CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL	CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL
800	1.900	0.25	1.9054	0.06	1.912	0.50	1.898	0.25	1.9034	0.0024	-0.003	0.002	0.009	-0.005	0.011	0.005	0.020	0.011	0.160	0.186	0.218	0.254

Results of the GO 0.3 sample

H_m (A/m)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i				$u(d_i)$				E_n			
	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL	CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL	CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL
2500	1.560	0.25	1.5537	0.06	1.570	0.50	1.553	0.25	1.5570	0.0032	0.003	-0.003	0.013	-0.004	0.010	0.007	0.017	0.010	0.151	0.248	0.385	0.198

Results of the NO 0.2 sample

H_m (A/m)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	x_{ref} (T)				$u(d_i)$				E_n			
	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL	CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL	CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL
800	1.901	0.40	1.9161	0.06	1.913	0.50	1.908	0.25	1.9113	0.0035	-0.010	0.005	0.002	-0.003	0.017	0.007	0.020	0.012	0.308	0.319	0.041	0.141

Results of the GO 0.18 sample

H_m (A/m)	Lab1		Lab2		Lab3		Lab4		x_{ref} (T)	$u(x_{ref})$ (T)	d_i				$u(d_i)$				E_n			
	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$	X	$u_x, \%$			CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL	CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL	CMI	PTB	INRIM	NPL
800	1.922	0.30	1.9118	0.06	1.912052	0.50	1.904	0.25	1.9120	0.0037	0.010	0.000	0.000	-0.008	0.014	0.008	0.020	0.012	0.366	0.013	0.000	0.333

Results of the Laser scribed GO 0.2 sample

GO 0.3

NO 0.2

GO 0.18

Laser scribed GO 0.2

7 Summary and conclusions

After the evaluation of the data in agreement with the rules of EURAMET the agreement of the comparison is very good, because E_n values smaller 1 are obtained for all data points. This report also confirms that the results are consistent with the declared uncertainty of each individual laboratory.

8 References

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